

**THE TRAVEL DAIRY OF THE AMBASSADOR, TOURIST
AND MERCHANT ANTONIO JENKINSON REFLECTS THE
INFORMATION ABOUT STATE MANAGEMENT IN THE
COUNTRIES OF CENTRAL ASIA**

¹Turaev Shukhrat Rakhmanovich

Karshi State University a teacher of Department of History of
Uzbekistan,

²Choriyev Jasur Beknazar o'g'li

Student of faculty of History of Karshi State University.

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7821407>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 03rd April 2023

Accepted: 11th April 2023

Online: 12th April 2023

KEY WORDS

Political, socio-economic, Soviet state, European tourist, diplomat, Ivan Grozny, map, cartographer, "unusual situation", the owner of the Juybor.

ABSTRACT

In this article, based on the work of Antonio Jenkinson, the author sheds on light on the issues of state management in Central Asia in the 16th century.

As a result of fundamental reforms in the political, economic, social, spiritual and cultural spheres during the establishment of the independent Republic of Uzbekistan and the development stage up to today, the studying our history of the new society's establishment on the basis of authentic historical sources written in different languages, especially through the translation of sources made it possible to analyze historical data in them and introduce them into scientific circulation.

After all, the one-sided use of sources in studying the history of our country during the time of the former Soviets led to the fact that our history was not covered objectively, and it was misinterpreted in many ways.

There are many sources written in local and European languages that shed light on the history of the events related to the era of Shaybanite's political, state administration and socio-economic life of our country in the 16th century and most of them belong to historians, ambassadors, merchants and tourists. Memoirs of the English ambassador, tourist and merchant Antonio Jenkinson are an important source especially in illuminating the socio-economic and political situation of this period. A comparative analysis and critical study of the information on the history of our country in this work based on local materials will make it possible to clarify many events.

Little is known about Antonio Jenkinson's life. His first journey dates back to his youth and he traveled until 1572. He was a sailor and skilled tradesman. He had been working for "Moscow Trading Company" for a long time and had successfully completed the company's tasks. English spy and diplomat Antonio Jenkinson (year of birth unknown- died 1610 or 1611) was the son-in-law of John Marsh whose the Governor of the Moscow Trading Company. He traveled a lot in Europe, Asia and Africa. He was the first representative of the

Lords of Liverpool and the ambassador of England in the government of Ivan Grozny. With the permission of the Russian Tsar Ivan Grozny, he visited Iran and Central Asia in 1558-59s and 1562-64s. In 1566, he became the first ambassador of England in Moscow. He performed several tasks in addition to diplomatic duties.

A map made by Antonio Jenkinson during his trip was published in London under the name "Description of Russia Muscovy and Tataria". This map has historical and scientific value. Jenkinson's map was included in the atlas when Abraham Artelii's Landscape of the Globe was published. Abraham Artelii (1527-1598y) was a Flemish geographer and cartographer.

In 1558, Antonio Jenkinson took a label from the Russian Tsar and set off from Moscow to Central Asia. Antonio Jenkinson and his partners spent 3 months (December 12, 1558 - March 2, 1559) in the Khanate of Bukhara with great difficulties. The tourist left valuable information about the city, its socio-economic life, the khan and his military forces, internal and external trade.

On July 14 of this year, Antonio Jenkinson and his companions arrived in Astrakhan. On July 27, he landed on the Mangishlaq (now Mangistau) peninsula on the shores of the Caspian Sea. At that time, the Caspian Sea was known as the Hazar Sea in Turkish languages, Bahri Hazar in Persian and Arabic languages, Caspian Sea in European languages. One of the important channels from the Caspian Sea to the interior of Central Asia is Mangishlaq, and the traveler wrote about the administration here: "These (earthly) soldiers were in the service of the country's king called Temur Sultan (Hajimkhan's brother). These Tatars stopped our caravans and collected taxes in the name of their king. They consume koumiss and meat. They have no bread. The king gave me a trade label.

From this information, it can be understood that the nomadic population lived around the north-western regions of the Caspian Sea - the Mangishlaq Peninsula (today's Mangistau region in Western Kazakhstan) and the Turko-Mongol people's lifestyle prevailed among them. When Antonio Jenkinson came to Mangishlaq, these territories belonged to the Genghisid dynasty whose center was in the city of Astrakhan (Ashtrakhan-Khoji Tarkhan), and the representative of this dynasty were descendants of Botukhan whose the ruler of the Golden Horde. Jenkinson's host was Genghisid ruler Timur Sultan, about whom traveler wrote:

"This sultan lives in the desert, without any city or palace. His residence is made of reeds and covered with carpets. The sultan asked me about our kingdom, its laws, its region, I was interrogated about the reasons for my coming here"

This information which describes the meeting of a tourist with one of the steppe, gives certain ideas about the socio-political and ethno-cultural life in the desert and steppe parts of Central Asia in the Middle Ages and helps to further increase the current understanding of the economic and household lifestyle of the nomadic population. Jenkinson who is a representative of a different culture which caused him to dwell on this issue in depth, such an "unusual situation" in the lifestyle of Asians was almost exceptional in Europe and its close neighbors by the Middle Ages.

Jenkinson's direct information about the city of Saraychik, one of the capitals of the White Horde ulus and its ruler, as well as Vazir and Urganch of the Khorezm provinces, are valuable. According to numismatic and written sources, the city of Saraychik was founded in the second

part of 13th century or the beginning of the 14th century and it is one of the centers of the White Horde. The traveler wrote about the city of Saraychik:

“One day’s journey from the Yayik River, there is a city called Saraychik (the ruins which are now located on the left bank of the Ural River). The city is ruled by the mayor Mirzo Ismoil. There is no trade. The inhabitants are warriors and herdsman”. It can be seen that the city was founded by nomads - Turko-Mongol people and this place was not a specific economic center, but a political center, and the inhabitants of the city consisted of nomads who began to settle in the city.

Also, about the administration of the Bukhara Khanate: “In Bukhara, the khan rules for two or three years at most. During this period, he is killed or expelled...”. From this information, it can be understood that until the accession of Abdullakhan II to the throne of the Bukhara Khanate in the middle of the 16th century, feudal disunity prevailed and the crown passed from hand to hand in the country.

In the work, some information about the Khan of Bukhara, Abdullakhan II was recorded, including: “On December 24, 1558, I met the Khan of Bukhara and presented him with the title of the Russian tsar. The khan welcomed me and invited me to the tablet. The khan asked me about the properties of the Russian tsar, the Russian state and its laws and asked about the Turkish sultan”.

“There is a religious leader in Bukhara and he controls the implementation of laws in the city. The people obey him more than the governor. The khan changes governors according to his wishes”. It is known from the scientific researches of the following years that there is talk about the owner of the Juybor Muhammad Islam and the governor of Bukhara Burkhan Sultan.

To sum up, the ambassador, traveler and merchant Antonio Jenkinson was the first traveler from the Russian in Europe where he traveled through Central Asia. In the 16th century, despite internal conflicts and internal struggles, A. Jenkinson managed to travel in different parts of region. He summarized the result of his travels in these countries in his work entitled “Travel from Moscow, Russia to Bukhara, Bactria in 1558”.

The information on the description of the Khanates of Bukhara and Khiva and its cities in Antonio Jenkinson's work was originally translated in Russian, by Y. Goethe in 1937. In 1988, his partial translations were published by B. V. Lunin. At the same time, information from Jenkinson's work can also be observed in the works of B.A. Akhmedov, A. Pankov. Although, there are some uncertainties and confusions in the information about the 16th century state management of our country written by Antonio Jenkinson, his 16th century statehood is incomparable value as an important historical source for studying our history.

References:

1. Дженкисон. А Путешествие в Среднюю Азию. 1558-1560гг. / Перевод с английского Й. В. Готе // Английские путешественники в Московском государстве в 16в. - Л.: Полиграф книга, 1937. - С. 167-192
2. Джураева Г. Новые данные по истории Бухары 16в.- М., 1988. - С.65.
3. Советская историческая энциклопедия. Т.6. - М., 1965. - С. 514-518.
4. Хасанов. Х. Урта Осиё жой номлари тарихидан. - Т.: Фан, 1965 - Б. 75

5. Лунин Б.В. История Узбекистана в источниках (Известия путешественников, географов и учёных 16 - первое половине 16 вв). - Т.: Фан. 1988. - С. 21-22; Абусейтова М. Х. и др. История Казахстана и Центральной Азии. - Алматы: "БІЛІМ" 2001. - С.332. Turaev, S. R. (2020). DESCRIPTION OF THE KHIVA KHANATE IN THE DIARY OF THE MEDIEVAL EUROPEAN TRAVELER, AMBASSADOR ANTHONY JENKINSON. Theoretical & Applied Science, (1), 736-739. Тураев, Ш. Р. (2022). ВИЗАНТИЯ МАНБАЛАРИДА ТУРК ХОҚОНЛИГИНИНГ СОСОНИЙЛАР ДАВЛАТИ ВА ВИЗАНТИЯ БИЛАН МУНОСАБАТЛАРИГА ОИД МАЪЛУМОТЛАР ТАҲЛИЛИ. ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ, 5(2). Rakhmanovich, T. S. (2022). Analysis of bizanty sources information on the turkish khanate's relationship with the sasanian state and Byzantian. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 12(4), 425-429. Икромов, Ш. И., Кучаров, Ж. К., Мамадалиев, Х. И., Тураев, Ш. Р., Сулайманова, С. Б., & Жумаева, Ш. Б. (2022). Мустақил Ўзбекистондаги трансформация жараёнларининг араб давлатларида ёритилиши. Образование, 8(9), 10.
6. Лунин Б. В. История Узбекистана в источниках (Известия путешественников географов, и учёных 16 - первое половине 16 вв). - Т.: Фан. 1988. - С. 24. Turaev Shukhrat Rakhmanovich. HISTORIC STUDY OF THE TRADITIONAL ECONOMY OF THE UZBEK PEOPLE FORMED IN ANCIENT AND MEDIEVAL CENTURIES. International Journal of Business diplomacy and Economy.1(4) 30-33. Turaev Shukhrat Rakhmanovich. DIFFERENCES BETWEEN THE JADID MOVEMENT THAT AROSE IN TURKESTAN IN THE LATE XIX - EARLY XX CENTURIES AND THE ANCIENT FIGURES OPPOSED TO THEM. International Journal of Business diplomacy and Economy.1(4) 24-29.
7. Юлдашев М. Ю. К истории торговых и посольских связей Средней Азии с Россией в 16-18 вв. - Т.: Наука, 1964. - С. 18-19. Turayev Shuxrat. O'rta asrlar Yevropa sayyohlarining asarlarida O'rta Osiyo tarixi va madaniyatining yoritilishi. T.f.f.d.dissertatsiyasi.Q., 2022. 87-94 b.
8. Ахмедов Б. А. Путешествие в Среднюю Азию Антони Дженкисона // Историко - географическая литература Средней Азии 16-18 вв. (Письменные памятники). - Т.: Фан, 1985. - С. 194-200.
9. Voyages de M.P.S. Pallas, en differentes provinces de Empire de Russie, et dans Asie septentrionale. T. 1. - Paris. Lagranger, 1978. - P. 485-486.
10. Таймасова Л. Ю. Зелье для государя. Английский шпионаж в России 16 столетия. - М.: Вече, 2010.-С. 368 (Тайны земли Русской).
11. Сагдуллаев А, Аминов Б, Мавлонов У, Норкулов Н. Ўзбекистон тарихи Давлат ва жамият тараккиёти. - Т. Академия. 2000. - 163б. Turayev Shuxrat. O'rta asrlar Yevropa sayyohlarining asarlarida O'rta Osiyo tarixi va madaniyatining yoritilishi. Monografiya .T., 2022. 105 b.